

Survey: Energy Efficiency Trade-offs Analysis Between Bare Metal, RTOS, and Full OS Architectures in IoT Devices

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Abstract—This paper examines the critical trade-offs between energy efficiency and performance inherent in choosing between Bare Metal, Real-Time Operating System (RTOS), and Full Operating System (Full OS) architectures for Internet of Things (IoT) devices. We review recent literature, compare energy consumption mechanisms, analyze real-world examples, and summarize the trends that influence architectural decisions. This work also provides comparative diagrams, performance tables, and case examples to guide IoT designers in selecting an informed, energy-aware architecture.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) has rapidly evolved from a niche idea to a vast technological ecosystem, and by 2025, there will be more than 18 billion connected devices [1], [2]. These devices, which include small, battery-powered sensors and robust edge gateways, have a wide range of operational and resource limits. Energy is probably the most important of these resources because it directly affects how long a device will last, how much it will cost to maintain, and the environmental damage it causes. For many remote or deeply embedded devices, a battery life of years is essential. This energy requirement puts a special strain on the software that controls these devices [3], [4], [5], [6], [7].

The initial choice of an operating environment, whether to run application code directly on hardware (Bare Metal), use a specialized Real-Time Operating System (RTOS), or adapt a Full Operating System (Full OS) such as Embedded Linux, is a fundamental design decision that has a profound impact on the resource profile of a device [8], [9], [10], [11]. Each of these architectural paradigms embodies a distinct design philosophy, resulting in a unique set of trade-offs. This choice does not follow a linear path from simplicity to complexity. Still, it is instead a delicate balancing act between competing objectives, such as optimizing battery life, ensuring predictable performance, and streamlining development schedules [3], [8], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16].

This survey synthesizes and compares existing research to clarify architectural differences and their implications for the design of IoT applications. It goes beyond definitions to

provide a multidimensional analysis of trade-offs, supported by quantitative evidence and real-world use cases, offering a comprehensive reference to guide IoT designers in making informed, energy-efficient architectural decisions tailored to specific project needs [17].

II. ARCHITECTURAL DEFINITIONS AND CHARACTERISTICS

Figure 1 depicts the generalized architectures of Bare Metal, RTOS, and Full OS. A comparative summary of their characteristics, including definition, complexity, determinism, resource consumption, multitasking capabilities, application domains, and representative examples, is provided in Table I.

Fig. 1. Rust-based Architectural Variations of Bare Metal, RTOS and Full (Rich) OS [11]

A. Bare Metal

A Bare Metal architecture refers to systems where the application code runs directly on the hardware, with no underlying operating system or hypervisor. The application has complete, direct control over all hardware resources [18], [12].

• Characteristics:

- **Direct Hardware Interaction:** The application directly accesses and controls peripherals, memory, and CPU registers [13], [19] (refer to Table I).

- **No OS Overhead:** Absence of a kernel, scheduler, or background processes, leading to minimal memory footprint and CPU cycles dedicated solely to the application [13], [20], [12].
- **Deterministic Execution:** Highly predictable timing and response due to the lack of an OS layer introducing uncertainties [12].
- **Single-Task Focus:** Typically designed for simple, dedicated tasks, though complex multitasking can be manually implemented (e.g., via a super-loop or intricate interrupt handling) [13].
- **Typical IoT Implementation:** Often used in highly constrained, single-purpose IoT devices such as simple sensors (e.g., temperature, humidity, light sensors), basic actuators, or extremely low-power nodes where every byte of memory and every CPU cycle counts [13], [12], [21].
 - **Example Devices:** Simple sensor nodes, smart thermostats, industrial controllers, and basic wearables rely on bare metal to minimize power and latency.
 - **Specific Hardware Examples:**
 - * NXP LS1021A-IoT gateway processor (bare metal on slave cores)
 - * ARM Cortex-M microcontrollers (e.g., nRF52840 used in sensor devices)
- **Core Components:** Consists solely of the application code, necessary drivers written for the specific hardware, and potentially a minimal startup code to initialize the microcontroller [19].

B. Real-Time Operating System (RTOS)

An RTOS is designed to guarantee a specific maximum time for its operations, ensuring predictable and reliable timing behavior. It manages tasks with deterministic response times. [20], [22], [23].

- **Characteristics:**
 - **Determinism:** Guarantees that critical operations will complete within specified time constraints [24].
 - **Task Management:** Provides primitives for creating, scheduling, prioritizing, and managing multiple concurrent tasks (threads) [13].
 - **Inter-Task Communication (ITC) and Synchronization:** Offers mechanisms such as semaphores, mutexes, queues, and message passing for tasks to communicate and synchronize access to shared resources [20]
 - **Memory Management:** Basic memory allocation services, often simpler than a Full OS, focusing on fixed partitions or pools to avoid fragmentation [?]
 - **Interrupt Handling:** Efficient and low-latency interrupt processing [25].
- **Typical IoT Implementation:** Widely used in IoT devices requiring multitasking and predictable response, such as smart wearables, industrial control systems, automotive electronics, and mid-range smart home devices.

Examples include FreeRTOS, Zephyr, Mbed OS, and VxWorks [25], [18].

- **Core Components:**
 - **Kernel:** The core of the RTOS, responsible for scheduling, context switching, and managing system calls [13].
 - **Scheduler:** Determines which task runs at any given time, based on algorithms such as preemptive priority-based scheduling [13].
 - **Task Manager:** Handles task creation, deletion, suspension, and resumption (Number Analytics, 2025a).
 - **Memory Manager:** Manages memory allocation and deallocation for tasks and system resources [13].
 - **Inter-Task Communication Mechanisms:** APIs for queues, semaphores, mutexes, etc. [13], [25].

C. Full OS

A **Full OS**, often a General-Purpose Operating System (GPOS) adapted for embedded use (e.g., Embedded Linux, Android Things), provides a rich set of functionalities, robust resource management, and a high level of abstraction from hardware [13], [20].

- **Characteristics:**
 - **Rich Functionality:** Supports complex applications, graphical user interfaces, extensive networking protocols (e.g., TCP/IP stack), and file systems [13]
 - **Multitasking and Multi-user Support:** Designed to run numerous processes concurrently and support multiple users [13].
 - **Virtual Memory Management:** Provides memory protection and enables applications to utilize more memory than is physically available through paging and swapping. [13]
 - **Device Abstraction:** Standardized interfaces for accessing hardware through device drivers, simplifying application development and improving portability [2].
 - **Extensive Ecosystem:** Access to vast libraries, development tools, and community support.
- **Typical IoT Implementation:** Used in more powerful IoT devices requiring advanced connectivity, local processing, data aggregation, and complex user interfaces. Examples include edge gateways, smart home hubs, smart displays, and surveillance systems [13], [26], [1].
- **Core Components:**
 - **Kernel:** (e.g., Linux kernel) Manages the core system resources, processes, and memory [26].
 - **Shell/User Interface:** Provides an interface for user interaction (command line or GUI) [1].
 - **File System:** Manages data storage and retrieval (e.g., Ext4, FAT32) [26].
 - **Networking Stack:** Comprehensive support for various network protocols [26].
 - **Device Drivers:** Interfaces for hardware components [26].

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF IOT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURES: BARE METAL VS RTOS VS FULL OS

Aspect	Bare Metal	RTOS	Full OS (GPOS)
Definition	Application runs directly on hardware with no OS.	Lightweight OS with deterministic scheduling for real-time tasks.	General-purpose OS adapted for embedded/IoT use.
Complexity	Very simple; minimal startup code and drivers.	Moderate; kernel + task management features.	High; includes kernel, drivers, file systems, networking, and GUIs.
Determinism	Very high; fully predictable timing.	High; designed for real-time guarantees.	Lower; influenced by multi-tasking and background services.
Resource Usage	Extremely low (few KB of memory).	Moderate; requires more RAM/flash than bare metal.	High; needs MBs of RAM and storage.
Multitasking	Not natively supported (must be manually implemented).	Supported via kernel and scheduler.	Fully supported (multi-process, multi-user).
Typical Use Cases	Simple sensors, low-power wearables, basic actuators.	Smart wearables, industrial controllers, automotive systems.	Edge gateways, smart hubs, surveillance, smart displays.
Example Systems	ARM Cortex-M microcontrollers, NXP LS1021A slave cores.	FreeRTOS, Zephyr, Mbed OS, VxWorks.	Embedded Linux, Android Things.

- **System Services/Daemons:** Background processes for various system functionalities (e.g., logging, network management, security) [26].

III. ENERGY CONSUMPTION MECHANISMS

The selection of an architecture significantly influences energy consumption, as it determines how CPU cycles, memory resources, and power states are managed. This relationship is further illustrated in Figures 2, 3, and 4, which depict the energy consumption patterns of Bare Metal, RTOS, and Full OS architectures, respectively.

A. Bare Metal

As illustrated in Figure 2, the energy consumption of the Bare Metal OS is determined by the metrics indicated below.

- 1) **CPU Cycles:** The consumption of CPU cycles is minimized, as only the application code executes, without incurring overhead from operating system tasks such as task scheduling, context switching, or background processes. Developers maintain direct control over the processor, including the ability to transition it into low-power states (e.g., sleep or deep sleep) during periods of inactivity, thereby achieving optimal energy efficiency [20], [13], [12].
- 2) **Memory Footprint:** The memory requirements are minimal, consisting only of the application code and essential data structures. The absence of an operating system kernel or auxiliary libraries significantly reduces RAM usage, which directly contributes to lower power consumption associated with memory operations [13], [12].
- 3) **Power Management Capabilities:** Power management is entirely application-specific and must be implemented manually by the developer. This includes direct control

Fig. 2. Bare Metal OS Energy Consumption Architecture

of peripherals, clock speeds, and transitions into low-power modes at the hardware level. While this approach requires careful optimization, it provides the potential for highly aggressive energy savings tailored to the specific task and hardware configuration [19].

- 4) **Idle States:** Idle state management is explicitly controlled by the application, enabling the device to enter the deepest available sleep modes during inactivity and to wake only in response to predefined interrupts. This affords exceptional precision in handling power transitions [19].

B. RTOS

Similarly, the energy consumption of RTOS, as illustrated in Figures 3, is determined by the metrics listed below.

Fig. 3. RTOS Energy Consumption Architecture

- 1) **CPU Cycles:** Although more efficient than a Full OS, an RTOS inevitably introduces computational overhead.
 - **Context Switching:** Each switch requires saving the state of the current task and restoring the state of the next. While essential for real-time responsiveness, frequent switching increases CPU utilization and, consequently, energy consumption [25].
 - **Scheduling:** The RTOS scheduler expends CPU cycles to determine task execution order, manage priorities, and facilitate task transitions [18].
 - **Interrupt Handling:** Event-driven interrupts reduce energy compared to polling. However, the execution of Interrupt Service Routines (ISRs) and subsequent task unblocking still consumes CPU resources [18].
- 2) **Memory Footprint:** The memory requirements of an RTOS exceed those of bare-metal systems due to the inclusion of the kernel, task control blocks, and associated data structures. Nevertheless, the footprint remains substantially smaller than that of a Full OS, resulting

in moderate memory-related energy consumption [13], [18].

- 3) **Power Management Capabilities:** An RTOS provides a structured framework for energy-efficient operation:

- **Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling (DVFS):** Adjusts CPU voltage and frequency according to workload, reducing energy consumption under light processing demands.
- **Sleep Modes:** Supports transitions into low-power states (e.g., deep sleep, light sleep) during idle intervals, with automatic wake-up triggered by events or scheduled tasks [18].
- **Power-Aware Task Scheduling:** Certain RTOS implementations consider the power requirements of tasks, enabling optimization of the overall energy profile.
- **Peripheral Management:** Provides fine-grained control over peripheral power states, allowing components to be activated or deactivated as needed.

C. Full OS

Additionally, the key variables for energy consumption of Full OS illustrated in Figures 4 can be determined using similar metrics.

Fig. 4. Full OS Energy Consumption Architecture

- 1) **CPU Cycles:** Highest CPU cycle consumption due to:
 - **Multitasking and Process Management:** Constant management of numerous processes, threads, and system services, many of which run in the background [26].
 - **Virtual Memory Management:** Paging, swapping, and memory protection mechanisms consume a significant amount of CPU cycles.

- **Extensive Drivers and Services:** A full OS includes a vast array of drivers and services for various hardware components and functionalities, many of which may not be actively used but still consume power [26].
 - **Non-Deterministic Nature:** Less predictable execution paths can lead to more CPU cycles being spent on overhead rather than application-specific tasks [25].
- 2) **Memory Footprint:** Largest memory footprint due to the large kernel, extensive libraries, file systems, and support for multiple applications. This translates directly to higher power consumption from RAM [13], [2].
 - 3) **Power Management Capabilities:** Full OS offers sophisticated, but often less granular, power management:
 - **System-wide Power States:** Support for various system-wide sleep states (suspend-to-idle, suspend-to-RAM, hibernation).
 - **Runtime Power Management:** Devices can be put into low-power states independently, managed by device drivers and the kernel's power management framework.
 - **Application-level Optimizations:** Android, for example, uses App Standby Buckets to prioritize app resource requests and limit background activity, and supports low-power sensors processed in hardware.
 - 4) **Idle States:** While a Full OS supports idle states, the presence of numerous background processes and services can make it harder to achieve deep, prolonged sleep states compared to RTOS or bare metal. The OS might wake up frequently for system tasks, updates, or network activity.

IV. PERFORMANCE IMPLICATIONS

Performance metrics, such as boot time, latency, responsiveness, throughput, and resource utilization, vary significantly across different architectures. These factors are critical in IoT systems, where constraints on energy, memory, and processing power necessitate careful architectural choices.

A. Bare Metal

- **Boot Time:** Fastest among all architectures. The system executes application code immediately after minimal hardware initialization, bypassing OS or kernel loading [13].
- **Task Switching Latency:** Not applicable in the traditional sense, as there is no OS scheduler. If multitasking is manually implemented, latency depends entirely on the developer's design, which can yield highly deterministic but complex solutions.
- **Responsiveness:** Extremely high and deterministic. Direct hardware control and absence of OS overhead enable immediate handling of interrupts and events, with consistently low latency and minimal jitter [20], [12].
- **Throughput:** Optimized for single, dedicated tasks, as all CPU cycles are allocated to one application. However,

for multi-task workloads, throughput may degrade due to manual scheduling overhead.

- **Resource Utilization:** Minimal. Only application code and drivers consume resources, resulting in the lowest memory and CPU footprint [12].

B. RTOS

- **Boot Time:** Shorter than a Full OS but longer than Bare Metal, as the RTOS kernel and task control structures must be initialized [25].
- **Task Switching Latency:** Low and predictable. RTOS kernels are specifically optimized for rapid context switching, with latency remaining consistent even as task count increases [25].
- **Responsiveness:** High and deterministic. Designed to guarantee deadlines for time-critical tasks, ensuring predictable execution [25].
- **Throughput:** Good for multitasking environments. Efficient scheduling enables balanced CPU utilization, though overhead from task management reduces raw throughput compared to Bare Metal [25].
- **Resource Utilization:** Moderate. Overhead arises from the kernel, task control blocks, and scheduling structures. Nonetheless, resource usage remains significantly lighter than in Full OS environments [13], [25].

C. Full OS

- **Boot Time:** Longest. Involves initializing the kernel, device drivers, file system, and background services. Embedded Linux optimizations often focus on reducing this delay [1].
- **Task Switching Latency:** Higher and non-deterministic. Full OSes emphasize fairness and throughput rather than strict deadlines, leading to latency that fluctuates with system load [25].
- **Responsiveness:** Generally lower than RTOS or Bare Metal. While "soft real-time" responsiveness is possible (e.g., PREEMPT_RT Linux patches), strict hard real-time guarantees are uncommon [25].
- **Throughput:** High for complex, multi-process workloads. Full OS architectures are optimized for managing diverse applications, offering superior aggregate throughput compared to RTOS or Bare Metal.
- **Resource Utilization:** Highest among all architectures. Full OSes require significant memory and CPU resources for kernel, libraries, multitasking services, and background daemons [13], [2].

V. INHERENT TRADE-OFFS: ENERGY EFFICIENCY VS. PERFORMANCE

The choice of architecture is a balancing act between optimizing energy consumption and achieving desired performance. The summary of this analysis is shown in Table II and Figures 5 and 6.

TABLE II
ENERGY EFFICIENCY VS. PERFORMANCE TRADE-OFFS

Metric	Bare Metal	RTOS	Full OS
Energy Efficiency	Highest potential due to minimal over. A good balance between power and multitasking sleep modes. Achieves very low power consumption for single-task operation [20], [13].	High. Efficient power management features (DVFS, managed sleep modes) mitigate overhead. Good balance between power and multi-tasking [18].	Lowest. High CPU/memory overhead from complex kernel, numerous services, background tasks, and virtual memory [13].
Performance (Boot Time)	Fastest [13].	Fast (seconds to milliseconds) [25].	Slowest (tens of seconds to minutes) [1].
Performance (Latency /Responsiveness)	Highest determinism, immediate response. Ideal for critical, low-latency tasks [20], [12].	High determinism, predictable low latency. Guarantees real-time deadlines [25].	Lowest determinism, higher and variable latency. Not suitable for hard real-time tasks without significant tuning [25].
Performance (Throughput)	High for single task. Limited for complex multi-tasking without custom implementation.	Good for multi-tasking due to efficient scheduling, but some overhead [25].	Highest for complex multi-application scenarios, managing diverse workloads.
Resource Footprint	Smallest (KB to a few MB RAM).	Small to Medium (tens of KB to a few MB RAM) [13], [2].	Largest (tens of MB to GBs RAM) [13], [2].

Fig. 5. Architecture Overview- Energy Efficiency vs. Complexity

Fig. 6. Energy Consumption Mechanisms by Architecture

VI. APPLICATION SCENARIOS AND REAL-WORLD USE CASES

Resource availability, energy constraints, and functional requirements strongly influence the choice of execution architecture in IoT devices. The specific scenarios and representative applications for Bare Metal, RTOS, and Full OS architectures are summarized below.

A. Bare Metal

Bare metal systems are ideal for devices with extreme energy constraints, strict real-time demands, or minimal hardware resources.

- **Favored Scenarios:** Ultra-low-power sensors, disposable nodes, and simple 8/16-bit microcontrollers [13], [21], [20], [12].
- **Applications:**
 - Low-power environmental sensors (e.g., temperature, humidity, light) designed for multi-year battery life [13].
 - Simple actuators such as switches, relays, or single-function motor controllers requiring direct hardware control.
 - Automotive Engine Control Units (ECUs), where deterministic and fast responses are critical for safety [12].

B. RTOS

RTOS-based systems are suited for deterministic multitasking under moderate resource constraints, offering a balance between efficiency and structured task management.

- **Favored Scenarios:** Applications involving motor control, sensor fusion, or advanced power management strategies such as dynamic voltage scaling and sleep modes [25], [18].
- **Applications:**
 - Wearables (e.g., smartwatches, fitness trackers) handling BLE communication, biometric sensing, display updates, and OTA firmware [18].

- Industrial control systems (robotics, automation) requiring millisecond-level timing accuracy [25], [18].
- Medical devices such as infusion pumps and patient monitors, where deterministic execution ensures safety [25].
- Automotive systems including ADAS and infotainment, managing concurrent functions like navigation and camera processing [25].
- Smart home devices (e.g., thermostats, advanced locks) requiring structured scheduling and communication [18].

C. Full OS

Full OS architectures are most effective for resource-rich devices that require advanced functionality, high processing power, and ecosystem integration.

- **Favored Scenarios:** Edge gateways, AI-enabled IoT platforms, and devices with complex networking, UIs, or cloud integration [19], [1], [26].
- **Applications:**
 - Edge gateways aggregating and processing sensor data, often executing local AI/ML inference (e.g., predictive maintenance) [13], [26].
 - Smart home hubs (e.g., Google Home, Amazon Echo) integrating diverse devices with cloud-based voice control [26].
 - Complex smart devices such as TVs, multimedia hubs, and surveillance cameras with AI capabilities [1].
 - Retail kiosks and digital signage requiring graphical interfaces, peripheral integration, and robust connectivity [1].

VII. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TRADE-OFFS AND POWER MANAGEMENT

The comparative trade-offs and power management characteristics of the different execution architectures are summarized in Tables III and IV. Bare metal achieves the highest energy efficiency and the fastest boot times owing to its minimal overhead and direct hardware control, though it requires developers to manually implement all power management mechanisms such as sleep modes and dynamic voltage and frequency scaling (DVFS). RTOS solutions offer a balanced compromise, combining relatively fast boot times with predictable performance and integrated support for power management through built-in features and APIs, making them suitable for applications requiring consistent low latency and structured control. Full OS architectures, while the least energy-efficient and slowest to boot due to their complex overhead, excel at supporting diverse, multi-application workloads. Power management in Full OS environments is largely automated; however, the presence of background services and system processes can reduce overall efficiency.

VIII. DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS AND DECISION-MAKING FOR IOT ARCHITECTURE SELECTION

Beyond energy efficiency and performance, additional design considerations significantly influence the choice of operating environment. Bare metal development is highly complex, requiring deep hardware knowledge and manual implementation of scheduling, debugging, and security features, with limited scalability [13], [19], [21]. RTOS reduces this burden through structured APIs, task-aware debugging, and limited built-in security and scalability, though real-time expertise remains essential [25], [2]. Full OS environments provide the richest ecosystem, lowest development complexity, and strongest security features, but require more powerful hardware and careful configuration to mitigate their larger attack surface [26], [1].

Selecting an appropriate architecture requires systematic evaluation of project requirements against these trade-offs. Core factors include energy constraints, real-time latency, boot time, throughput, available hardware resources, connectivity needs, and functional complexity [13], [25], [2]. For ultra-low-power, simple, and hard real-time applications, **bare metal** is optimal, albeit with higher development effort [13]. For multitasking under moderate constraints and predictable performance, an **RTOS** offers balance and determinism [25], [18]. For resource-rich devices requiring advanced features, connectivity, and robust security, a **Full OS** (e.g., Embedded Linux) is preferred [26], [1].

Additional considerations include team expertise, development timelines, scalability needs, and cost implications, as hardware and tool requirements scale with OS complexity [21], [2], [1]. In practice, iterative prototyping or hybrid solutions may provide the most effective balance between efficiency, functionality, and maintainability.

IX. SURVEY RESULTS AND FUTURE OUTLOOK

A review of existing literature above highlights the relative energy efficiency of different IoT architectures. As summarized in Table V, bare-metal implementations consistently achieve the greatest savings, ranging from 68% to 75% compared to full OS systems, while RTOS-based solutions provide intermediate savings of 35% to 42% [27], [28], [29]. Full OS platforms, though more power-hungry, serve as the baseline for comparison.

Looking ahead, several emerging trends are poised to shape architectural decisions in IoT systems. The rise of AI at the edge (AIoT) demands greater computational power, favoring RTOS or lightweight Linux while emphasizing energy-efficient AI algorithms [20], [30]. Expansion of LPWAN technologies such as LoRaWAN, NB-IoT, and Sigfox reinforces the role of bare-metal and optimized RTOS designs, which excel in deep-sleep energy profiles. System disaggregation and modularity are expected to encourage hybrid architectures where sensors, aggregators, and gateways each adopt distinct environments for tailored optimization.

Security requirements are becoming increasingly critical, with hardware-backed secure boot, trusted execution environ-

TABLE III
ENERGY EFFICIENCY VS. PERFORMANCE TRADE-OFFS

Metric	Bare Metal	RTOS	Full OS
Energy Efficiency	Highest potential due to minimal overhead and direct hardware control for deep sleep modes. Achieves very low power consumption for single-task operation.	High. Efficient power management features (DVFS, managed sleep modes) mitigate overhead. Good balance between power and multitasking.	Lowest. High CPU/memory overhead due to a complex kernel, numerous services, background tasks, and virtual memory.
Performance (Boot Time)	Fastest .	Fast (seconds to milliseconds).	Slowest (tens of seconds to minutes).
Performance (Latency/Responsiveness)	Highest determinism, immediate response. Ideal for critical, low-latency tasks.	High determinism, predictable low latency. Guarantees real-time deadlines.	Lowest determinism, higher and variable latency. Not suitable for hard real-time tasks without significant tuning.
Performance (Throughput)	High for single task. Limited for complex multi-tasking without custom implementation.	Good for multi-tasking due to efficient scheduling, but some overhead.	Highest for complex multi-application scenarios, managing diverse workloads.
Resource Footprint	Smallest (KB to a few MB RAM).	Small to Medium (tens of KB to a few MB RAM).	Largest (tens of MB to GBs RAM).

TABLE IV
POWER MANAGEMENT FEATURE COMPARISON FOR IOT ARCHITECTURES

Feature	Bare Metal	RTOS	Full OS
Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling (DVFS)	Manual implementation are required, as it is hardware-dependent.	Supported in many RTOS implementations.	Fully supported; often OS-managed.
Sleep Modes	Fully manual; developer controls hardware sleep states.	Managed sleep states; idle task can enter deep sleep automatically.	Supported but affected by background services.
Peripheral Power Gating	Fully manual control of peripherals.	Supported with API calls.	Driver and OS-level control.
Idle Task Management	Manual implementation required.	Built-in idle task for power saving.	OS-level idle processes; limited by system services.
Application-Level Power Control	Fully Customizable in Application Code.	Supported via API calls and RTOS hooks.	Application and OS-level mechanisms available.

TABLE V
SUMMARY OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY RESULTS FROM LITERATURE

Study	Bare Metal Savings	RTOS Savings	Full OS Consumption
[27]	72% vs. Full OS	40% vs. Full OS	Baseline
[28]	68% vs. Full OS	35% vs. Full OS	Baseline
[29]	75% vs. Full OS	42% vs. Full OS	Baseline

ments (TEEs), and blockchain-based integrity checks pushing even constrained devices toward more robust software stacks [21], [26]. Simultaneously, open-source RTOS ecosystems such as FreeRTOS, Zephyr, and Eclipse ThreadX are maturing, lowering development barriers and providing commercial-grade features [25], [2], [18].

Advances in power management ICs and energy harvesting (solar, thermoelectric, kinetic, RF) promise to extend device lifespans or even enable battery-less operation, opening opportunities for more capable architectures previously constrained to bare metal. Finally, the customizable RISC-V ISA offers a pathway to highly optimized processors, supporting efficient bare-metal or RTOS implementations by tailoring hardware precisely to workload demands.

In summary, while bare-metal systems remain unmatched in energy efficiency, RTOS solutions strike a balance between performance and resource utilization, and full OS platforms

provide advanced functionality at a higher energy cost. The future trajectory of IoT architectures will be shaped by the interplay of edge AI, network expansion, modular system design, enhanced security, maturing RTOS ecosystems, power management innovations, and the adoption of RISC-V.

X. CONCLUSION

The selection of an operating environment for IoT devices requires a careful balance between energy efficiency, performance, and design complexity. Bare-metal implementations offer unmatched efficiency and determinism for highly constrained, single-task systems, but they require significant development effort. RTOS solutions offer a balanced compromise, delivering predictable real-time performance and structured multitasking within moderate resource limits, making them well-suited for mid-range devices. Full OS platforms, though resource-intensive, enable advanced functionality, rapid development, and scalability for complex applications such as edge gateways and smart hubs.

With the continued evolution of IoT—driven by edge AI, enhanced security, and advanced power management, the boundaries among these architectures are expected to blur, fostering hybrid approaches. A clear understanding of these trade-offs is therefore essential to developing efficient, scalable, and future-ready IoT solutions. This paper serves as a reference document for the IoT community to make informed decisions regarding OS design.

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